

FINANCIAL LITERACY – THE KEY TO SPARK ENTREPRENEURIAL SPIRIT IN THE YOUNGER GENERATION

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ABSTRACT

The paper delves into the essential characteristics and features of financial literacy, focusing on a study conducted among the undergraduates from various engineering specialities at the Technical University of Varna. The research aimed to establish the level of financial literacy among the younger generation and provide recommendations for its enhancement.

Keywords: financial literacy, entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial activity, finance.

1. Financial literacy and entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurial activity is a complex set of processes and events undertaken by individuals with potential in a rapidly evolving and competitive business environment. The current globalized economy, with its multicultural dimensions, emphasizes the development of knowledge as a powerful catalyst for success [1,4,6,7]. Additionally, the integration processes within Europe are instrumental in shaping modern business ventures. Today's youth are confronted with a multitude of challenges related to their financial stability and prosperity. Balancing increasing personal responsibility with the diverse and complex array of financial products and services presents a serious dilemma for individuals when making financial decisions [2,3,8].

It is imperative to implement appropriate interventions aimed at enhancing the financial knowledge and skills of the younger generation/undergraduates in order for them to effectively manage limited financial resources, navigate economic uncertainty, and advocate for their rights [9,10,11]. Therefore, initiatives in the field of improving financial literacy should be viewed as an investment in human capital, fostering sustainable economic and social development. This, in turn, requires a shift in the process of training and a transformation of the traditional university model into a more entrepreneurial establishment of higher education. The primary objective of such a model should be to cultivate innovative thinking and entrepreneurial mindset among both students and lectures, while fostering collaboration with the business sector.

Financial literacy equips young individuals/undergraduates with the understanding of financial products and concepts, enabling them to develop the necessary skills to enhance their financial culture, i.e. to recognize financial risks and favourable opportunities for entrepreneurial growth, to empower them to make objective and informed decisions when selecting financial services.

More specifically, financial literacy encompasses a blend of financial knowledge, skills, motivation, and confidence in utilizing these capabilities when making sound financial decisions, with the ultimate outcome being the overall improvement in the well-being of individuals and society as a whole, ensuring fruitful participation of individuals in the economy (as stated in PISA) [8].

From a wider perspective, financial literacy plays a crucial role in driving the demand for financial products due to the recognized benefits they offer, producing, thereby, a powerful impact on the market growth. Similarly, consumers who are financially literate—those who are aware of their legal rights, understand their responsibilities, and being well-informed—through their informed choices and the exercise of their rights, contribute to the advancement of market competition [5,6,11].

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) identifies financial training (education) as a key tool in positively affecting the level of financial literacy [8]. Financial education can be defined as “*a process by which consumers increase their understanding of financial products and basic financial concepts, and through information, guidance, and objective advice, they tend to develop the skills and confidence needed to comprehend financial risks and opportunities, to make rational and informed decisions, to know where to seek assistance, and be capable of taking effective actions to improve their financial well-being*”.

2. Assessment of the youth financial literacy and its impact on their entrepreneurial activity (a case study of the students from TU-Varna)

Investing in education and training to develop skills is essential for promoting growth and competitiveness. In today's knowledge-based economies, there is a demand for highly qualified individuals who can meet specific needs. According to Cedefop forecasts, the proportion of jobs in the EU requiring higher education is expected to increase from 29% in 2023 to 34% by 2028, while the number of low-skilled jobs during the same period is projected to decrease from 23% to 18% [8].

Universal skills such as practical thinking, initiative, problem-solving ability, and prompt decision-making in crisis situations are essential for preparing individuals for a wide range of professional fields, which are increasingly diverse and unpredictable today.

It is crucial to prioritize the development of entrepreneurial skills, as they not only enable individuals to start their own businesses but also improve their employability. Furthermore, to effectively navigate future professional responsibilities in a rapidly changing environment, students must also possess certain financial skills.

The current paper presents a study into the entrepreneurial attitudes and financial literacy of students conducted through a survey. The survey was designed to measure the following key indicators: what entrepreneurial attitudes exist among the students; what range of financial skills and knowledge they possess; and what aptitude for decision-making they have. The survey was conducted among students from various engineering specialties at TU-Varna, spanning from the 1st to the 4th -year including fully engineering specialties, such as Computer Systems and Technologies (CST), Software and Internet Technologies (SIT), Transport Engineering and Technologies (TET), Navigation (N), Mechanical Engineering and Technologies (MET), and

others), as well as hybrid specialties, namely Industrial Management (IM) and Technological Entrepreneurship and Innovations (TEI), which incorporate financial courses. Altogether, a total of 70 randomly selected respondents participated in the study.

When asked: “Have you studied subjects related to entrepreneurship and finance?”, the students from the engineering specialties reported that they had not taken such courses, but they had acquired knowledge in these areas due to their interest in opportunities for additional income. Conversely, all students in the IM and TEI specialties had received training in subjects like entrepreneurship and finance (Fig.1).

Fig.1 Subjects in the field of entrepreneurship and finance studied by the students at TU-Varna

The results of the study reveal that 65% of the students in engineering specialties lack confidence in their ability to start their own business. Only 35% of them have plans to launch a business. Notably, entrepreneurial initiative and intent to venture into business are particularly low among students in CST, SIT and N area of specialization. In contrast, 60% of the students in the

IM specialty express a desire to start their own business, 30% feel uncertain about their capabilities, and 10% declared no intentions of pursuing business undertaking. Similar trends are observed among students in the TEI specialty, with 55% aspiring to start their own business, 30% feeling unsure about their success, and 15% - lacking interest in entrepreneurship (Fig.2).

Fig.2 Have you considered the idea of starting your own business?

A significant percentage of the young individuals aspiring to launch their own business intend to finance their ventures via a bank loan (70%), while 20% plan to utilize personal funds, and 10% aim to secure funding through EU programs.

Interestingly, 60% of the students in the IM and TEI specialties maintain a personal /family budget with specified expense categories as opposed to the engineering students with only 20% of them having a personal budget at hand.

Fig. 3 Relative share of students allocating funds for emergency expenses and a pension fund

It is evident from Fig. 3 that a mere 25% of the fully engineering students allocate funds for emergency expenses, and only 10% contribute to a pension fund. 75% of them do not allocate money for unexpected costs or a retirement fund, citing the “lack of necessity” as the primary reason. Meanwhile, 100% of the students in IM and TEI specialties set aside financial resources for unexpected costs, with 40% of them contributing to a pension fund.

Approximately 70% of the students surveyed do not have investments in financial assets such as stocks, bonds, and others. The highest proportion of investments in financial assets comes from the students in the IM specialty at 28%, followed by the fully engineering specialties at 25%, and the TEI specialty – 15%.

Fig.4 Relative share of investments in financial assets

80% of students utilize online banking as a payment method, with other financial technologies such as Revolut, Binance, Kiwi, and Wise also being commonly used.

Additionally, the students specializing in IM and TEI possess the skills needed to determine anticipated returns and profits from investments in financial assets, indicating their strong financial background.

3. Opportunities to enhance financial literacy among students

There exists a perfect opportunity to enhance financial literacy among students within the higher education system, considering, on one hand, their young age, and, on the other hand, the notable absence of sustainable education in personal finance. Addressing this gap, therefore, is imperative. In practice, young adults are increasingly entrusted with managing their personal finances and making significant financial decisions that can impact their future well-being, and it is, thus, vital for them to make informed decisions in this regard. The autonomy of

higher education institutions represents a major factor for increasing students' financial literacy by redesigning the curricula of specialties offered at various academic departments. In adherence to the regulatory requirements for curriculum structuring, there arise a possibility for partial or complete integration of financial literacy courses as elective or optional subjects within the curriculum, subject to approval from academic leadership and declared willingness on their part to prioritize financial literacy education. It is quite possible, on account of the expectations for enhanced practical training of the students and strengthened connections with employer organisations, for expert practitioners to be invited as guest lecturers to share valuable insights on specific topics related to financial literacy, regardless of the professional field in which the students are being trained. Another possibility includes coordinating research endeavours within and across higher education institutions with a particular emphasis on advancing financial literacy knowledge. The financial sector plays a pivotal role in this process, not only as a provider of financial services but also as a source of potential employment for students. It is advisable, in this regard, to organize an adequate process to facilitate knowledge transfer and exchange of ideas on current issues with students, which allows for flexibility in format and methods of manifestation: short internships; open days; digital educational resources; and podcasts. Adoption of informal learning methods is also a viable approach. New training channels can be established, to that effect, or existing ones can be further developed outside the formal education system. Within this framework, for example, in the department of Industrial Management guest lecturers have made significant contributions to the educational process by addressing specific topics related to financial literacy. Outstanding results are also achieved through the implementation of dual training methods, which, regrettably, have not yet been introduced in the Bulgarian higher education system, despite the existence of such a strategy.

4. Conclusion

Developing an entrepreneurial and financial mindset among the younger generation should commence during their university years, fostering a culture of openness to innovations and maintaining an entrepreneurial environment within the business sector. The drive to generate entrepreneurial ideas is closely linked to the expectation of success, which is rooted in identifying market needs, adapting to changes in market dynamics, and seizing opportunities to fill market niches.

The education of young adults/students must address the pressing demand of the Bulgarian economy for a new generation of skilled managers and entrepreneurs who are well-versed in contemporary practices and possess the practical skills needed to achieve sustainable growth and development. In view of this, universities and the government should prioritize the following initiatives:

- Implementing training programs based on real-life business scenarios— produced in collaboration with industry partners and organisations, and

complemented by a series of interactive business simulations;

- Embracing a hands-on teaching approach – utilizing the latest concepts, practices, and business tools in the field of entrepreneurship, management, finance, and innovation, drawing inspiration from the interactive teaching and learning approach adopted in leading global educational institutions;

- Facilitating knowledge sharing and experience exchange among students to cultivate lasting professional relationships;

- Inviting guest lecturers from the business and financial sectors to provide valuable insights and share their expertise with students;

- Providing training, guidance and support to young individuals regarding opportunities for launching their own ventures;

- Providing consultancy services to the adolescents on about intellectual property issues;

- Assisting students in securing financial resources and funding to start their entrepreneurial endeavours;

- Offering support to startups founded by recent graduates to help them navigate the challenges of the business landscape;

- Equipping teams with the necessary skills to participate in EU programs focused on research and technology.

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